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Horizon 2020

Call: H2020-MSCA-IF-2020
(Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellowships)

Topic: MSCA-IF-2020

Type of action: MSCA-IF-GF
(Global Fellowships)

Proposal number: 101028610

Proposal acronym: DARKSKY

Deadline Id: H2020-MSCA-IF-2020

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How to fill in the forms

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1 - General information

Topic MSCA-IF-2020

Type of Action MSCA-IF-GF

Call Identifier H2020-MSCA-IF-2020

Deadline Id H2020-MSCA-IF-2020

Acronym

Proposal title

Note that for technical reasons, the following characters are not accepted in the Proposal Title and will be removed: < > " &

Duration of outgoing phase in 3rd country

Scientific Area

Please select up to 5 descriptors (and at least 3) that best characterise the subject of your proposal, in descending order of relevance.

Descriptor 1

Descriptor 2

Descriptor 3

Descriptor 4

Descriptor 5

Free keywords

Please choose the scientific area and descriptors carefully, and in order of importance, since this will guide the REA in the selection of experts for proposal evaluation and the allocation of proposals to experts. To help you select the most relevant area for your proposal, please consult the Guide for Applicants which provides a breakdown of each scientific area into a number of descriptors.

Abstract*

This proposal seeks to construct a model which measures the carbon footprint of an individual tourism activity, informed by dark sky tourism (DST). Using mixed methods, I will calculate the emissions of dark sky areas (DSAs), and the tourists who visit them, while assessing the environmental sustainability of DST as a whole. The work involves (1) an international, comparative, qualitative study of staff and volunteers working in DSAs in Namibia, South Africa, the UK, and Ireland; (2) longitudinal surveys of DSA visitors; and (3) grey literature analysis. The results will feed into the model assembly, and will impact several academic disciplines (e.g. climate development, sustainable tourism, light pollution, science communication). Via engagement with relevant stakeholders, I will effectively disseminate the newfound knowledge amongst rural communities, policymakers and the tourism industry on global scales. The project will be carried out in three different locations – the Wester Ross Biosphere (secondment); the University of Namibia (outgoing phase); and the University of Oxford (incoming phase) – and will build on my previous expertise in astrophysics, astronomy communication, and astrotourism. As well as developing personal skills such as leadership and project management, I will acquire new skills in qualitative and quantitative research. Under the close supervision of a diverse team, and through specific training courses and training-through-research, the MSCA Global Fellowship will empower me to bridge the gap between astronomy and society while furthering the UN's 2030 Agenda and the EU's Green Deal, by reaching independence and fostering a new interdisciplinary research group.

Remaining characters

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Has a similar proposal in terms of research objectives been submitted to a Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellowship call?

Yes No

Dark sky tourism overlooked: a low-carbon solution to global tourism's rising footprint?

1.1 Quality and credibility of the research/innovation project; level of novelty, appropriate consideration of inter/multidisciplinary and gender aspects

This proposal seeks to construct a model which measures the carbon footprint of an individual tourism activity, informed by dark sky tourism (DST). Using mixed methods, I will calculate the emissions of dark sky areas (DSAs), and the tourists who visit them, while assessing the environmental sustainability of DST as a whole. The work involves (1) an international, comparative, qualitative study of staff and volunteers working in DSAs; (2) longitudinal surveys of DSA visitors; and (3) grey literature analysis. The results will feed into the model assembly, and will impact several academic disciplines (e.g. climate development, sustainable tourism, light pollution, science communication). Via engagement with relevant stakeholders, I will effectively disseminate the newfound knowledge amongst rural communities, policymakers and the tourism industry on global scales. The project will be carried out in three different locations – the Wester Ross Biosphere (secondment, with xxx); the University of Namibia (outgoing phase, with xxx); and the University of Oxford (incoming phase, with xxx and xxx) – and will build on my previous expertise in astrophysics, astronomy communication, and astrotourism. As well as developing personal skills such as leadership and project management, I will acquire new skills in qualitative and quantitative research. Under the close supervision of a diverse team, and through specific training courses and training-through-research, the MSCA Global Fellowship will empower me to bridge the gap between astronomy and society while furthering the UN's 2030 Agenda, by reaching independence and fostering a new interdisciplinary research group.

One of the fastest growing economic sectors globally, travel and tourism is a double-edged sword. On the one hand, the industry is an essential contributor to job and wealth creation, poverty alleviation, environmental conservation, and the protection of cultural heritage¹ – but on the other, exponentially increasing numbers of tourists is environmentally unsustainable, and a significant contributor to global greenhouse gas emissions^{2,3}. The climate emergency necessitates the need for the decarbonisation of the tourism industry – which cannot be achieved by technological advances alone³ – and thus, we must find and critically examine tourist activities which can serve the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) while transforming the sector toward carbon neutrality. Yet, there is no model in place which can measure the footprint of an individual activity, making it challenging to assess and compare different tourism segments. Such a model could lead to the formulation of a footprint index, to effectively inform and put pressure on the sector and motivate positive environmental change globally. Dark sky tourism is an excellent candidate with the potential to offer numerous insights, and will inform the timely creation of the carbon footprint model.

A nascent segment of ecotourism, DST makes use of unpolluted nightscapes as its fundamental resource⁴. Driven by increasing rates of urbanisation⁵, more than 80% of the world's population live under light-polluted skies⁶, making rural areas highly attractive tourism destinations. By way of example, the Colorado Plateau is estimated to generate \$5.8B over the next decade, creating more than 10,000 additional jobs annually⁷. DST supports sustainability under four main contexts: rural communities^{8,9}, light pollution^{10,11}, health and well-being^{12,13}, and education^{9,14}. However, it remains unclear whether DST is environmentally

¹ World Tourism Organization and United Nations Development Programme (2017), *Tourism and the Sustainable Development Goals – Journey to 2030*, UNWTO, Madrid

² P. Peeters & M. Landré (2012) *The Emerging Global Tourism Geography—An Environmental Sustainability Perspective*. Sustainability 4:42-71

³ M. Lenzen, et al. (2018) *The carbon footprint of global tourism*. Nature Climate Change 8:522–528

⁴ D. Weaver (2011) *Celestial ecotourism: new horizons in nature-based tourism*, Journal of Ecotourism, 10(1):38-45

⁵ H. Ritchie (2018) *Urbanization*, <https://ourworldindata.org/urbanization> [accessed 3/8/20]

⁶ F. Falchi, et al. (2016) *The new world atlas of artificial night sky brightness*. Sci. Adv. 2, e1600377

⁷ D. Mitchell & T. Gallaway (2019), *Dark sky tourism: economic impacts on the Colorado Plateau Economy, USA*, Tourism Review, 74(4):930-942

⁸ L. Jacobs, et al. (2020) *To wish upon a star: Exploring Astro Tourism as vehicle for sustainable rural development*, Development Southern Africa, 37(1):87-104

⁹ E. Blundell et al. (2020) *Dark sky tourism and the sustainability of regional tourism destinations*, Tourism Recreation Research.

¹⁰ D. A. Silver & G. M. Hickey (2020): *Managing light pollution through dark sky areas: learning from the world's first dark sky preserve*, Journal of Environmental Planning and Management

¹¹ D. Lapostolle & S. Challéat (2020) *Making Darkness a Place-Based Resource: How the Fight against Light Pollution Reconfigures Rural Areas in France*, Annals of the American Association of Geographers

¹² R. Bell, et al. (2014) *Dark Nature: Exploring potential benefits of nocturnal nature-based interaction for human and environmental health*. European Journal of Ecopsychology, 5.

¹³ A. Blair. (2018) *An Exploration of the Role that the Night Sky Plays in the Lives of the Dark Sky Island Community of Sark*. Journal of Skyscape Archaeology, 3(2):236-252

¹⁴ F. M. Collison & K. Poe (2013) "Astronomical Tourism": *The Astronomy and Dark Sky Program at Bryce Canyon National Park*. Tourism Management Perspectives 7:1–15

sustainable – a carbon footprint calculation would rectify this, thereby allowing for new de-growth solutions to be identified and communicated to tourism stakeholders. Possible reasons for DST's low-carbon footprint have been suggested in the aforementioned literature, although they have never been quantified: (1) energy savings and ecosystem conservation from reducing artificial light at night; (2) attracts large numbers of domestic tourists who do not need to fly; (3) rebalances demand, spreading the load from high-peak summer times toward off-peak times when the nights are longer; (4) light pollution education leads to behavioural changes – tourists engage in minimising light pollution in their communities when they return home.

Research methodology and approach. The work plan for this project consists of four specific tasks, as addressed by the following work packages (WPs). The research will be carried out under the expertise of xxx (Wester Ross) and xxx (Environmental Change Institute, Oxford) with further training and facilitation from xxx (Physics, Oxford) and xxx (Physics, UNAM). Guided by inclusionary and exclusionary criteria, e.g. only certified DSAs will be involved, namely those accredited by the International Dark-Sky Association (IDA), the Royal Astronomical Society of Canada (RASC), or the Starlight Foundation.

1. **An international, comparative, qualitative study of workers and volunteers in DSAs.** This first WP consists of ~20 semi-structured, in-depth interviews of a wide range of employees and volunteers in dark sky workplaces. Additional interviews will take place as necessary, to ensure that saturation has been reached. The majority of interviews will take place in person, in International Dark Sky Places (IDSPs) in Namibia, South Africa, the UK and Ireland. Additional online interviews will occur in certified DSAs on other continents to reach a global perspective. The interviews will explore how DSAs aid or harm environmental conservation in the eyes of the personnel, and how it relates to indigenous, cultural, and gender aspects. It will also be notable to identify differences between those who are paid or those who share knowledge voluntarily. The data will be analysed by thematic analysis, and in combination with longitudinal surveys (WP 2) and grey literature analysis (WP 3), will inform the development of the footprint model (WP 4).
2. **Longitudinal surveys of tourists and travellers in global DSAs.** Currently, there are at least 130 IDSPs, 19 RASC Dark-Sky Preserves, and 14 Starlight Reserves worldwide. In cooperation with the IDA, RASC, and the Starlight Foundation, numbers of visitors to 150+ DSAs will be monitored, and self-completion questionnaires will be completed by at least 1,000 tourists for the duration of one year. The survey will contain both quantitative and open-ended questions, in order to quantify carbon movements, stay duration, levels of consumption, and thoughts on the environmental sustainability of DST. Participants can also share demographic information if they are willing, to monitor inclusion and diversity aspects. They will also be offered a chance to opt-in and take part in a follow-up survey 6-months later, which will assess any changes in attitude or behaviour as a result of visiting a DSA. Previous studies have suggested that dark sky tourists are more inclined to advocate for reducing light pollution in their communities after returning home. This has never been quantified, but if true, could lead to significant carbon reductions. The data will be evaluated using typical descriptive statistics.
3. **Grey literature study.** The IDA requires annual reports from IDSPs to ensure that designated places are continuing their commitment to dark sky preservation. Each report contains estimated numbers of site visitors, as well as any new information on lighting, sky quality, outreach, funding, conservation, research, etc. Similar reports are required by the RASC, every two years. These data will serve to complement and triangulate the findings from WPs 1 and 2.
4. **Construction of the DST carbon footprint model.** Using the data acquired by the first three WPs, a carbon footprint model will be designed, focusing mainly on all direct emissions (and indirect emissions where possible), also informed by previous models in the literature^{3,15,16,17}. The model will be state-of-the-art, significantly advancing the field, allowing for others to estimate and compare the footprint of different tourism activities, and enabling the development of a carbon footprint index for tourism activities.

Originality and innovative aspects. This will be the first carbon footprint tourism model informed by quantitative and qualitative data. On the whole, mixed methods is little employed in sustainable tourism research – only 12% of papers published in the *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* between 2005-2014 were based on mixed methods¹⁸. The reason for this is easily explained – mixed methods is much more time-consuming than monomethod studies. The benefits far outweigh the hindrances, however – mixed methods

¹⁵ Y.-Y. Sun, et al. (2020) *Measuring the carbon footprint of wine tourism and cellar door sales*, Journal of Cleaner Production, 266:121937

¹⁶ M. Gold, et al. (2017) *The sustainable tourism index: enhancing the global travel environment*, The Economist Intelligence Unit

¹⁷ H. Sharp, et al. (2016) *Carbon Footprint of Inbound Tourism to Iceland: A Consumption-Based Life-Cycle Assessment including Direct and Indirect Emissions*. Sustainability 8:1147

¹⁸ J. F. Molina-Azorín & X. Font (2016) *Mixed methods in sustainable tourism research: an analysis of prevalence, designs and application in JOST (2005–2014)*, Journal of Sustainable Tourism, 24(4):549-573

can purposefully promote societal change¹⁸. Several more gaps in the sustainable tourism literature have already been highlighted, e.g. few studies explore tourism and climate change in less developed countries, or on the challenge posed by climate change on tourism and its ability to contribute to the SDGs¹⁹. Moreover, the majority of research uses single-destination case studies, and acutely lacks longitudinal data²⁰. Therefore, this proposal will provide exciting new insights in areas where many unknowns remain.

Additionally, the proposal fosters a highly innovative mix of stakeholders. Before now, astrophysicists and social scientists have rarely worked together, and in combination with tourism experts in industry (via Wester Ross), DARKSKY presents an exciting and novel collaboration.

Interdisciplinarity. DST naturally lends itself to being highly interdisciplinary. Supervised by experts in social science, tourism, and astrophysics, the work will be disseminated across several disciplines in academia (e.g. tourism, sustainable climate development, science communication, light pollution) and beyond (industry/policy). For the fellowship's duration, I will collaborate extensively across these multidisciplinary fields, while fostering a new dark sky tourism network. Strong links with academics in other departments at the host and outgoing institutions will provide further interdisciplinary input and expertise. This includes xxx (Oxford) and xxx (UNAM), whose main interests are environmental education and sustainable development. At each institution, I will also host cross-disciplinary meetings to foster a unique gathering of minds with very different backgrounds, so that we may question and discover new avenues of research pertaining to DST and sustainability.

Finally, my time during the secondment at the Wester Ross Biosphere in Scotland will enhance my engagement with rural communities, the tourism industry, and policy makers. I will live in a very rural area with minimal light pollution, working with experts on cultural heritage and sustainable tourism. Wester Ross is strongly associated with local and international tourism projects, and will provide invaluable opportunities for me to work directly with local government and councillors in the area, while improving my skills in science policy. In exchange, Wester Ross will benefit from my knowledge of astronomy and dark sky tourism, for which they have no prior experience and are very interested to learn more.

Gender dimension. Tourism will never be sustainable without the integration of gender equality within tourism development²¹, yet academically, there is little dialogue between gender and tourism research²². What role do women play when it comes to DST and environmental sustainability? Academically, women are underrepresented in astronomy (c.f. ASTROMOVES, MSCA-IF-2019), is this also reflected in DST – is there a gender difference between those who work in or visit DSAs? Under the supervision of xxx, an expert in gender and climate development in the Global South²³, I will ensure that the gender dimension is questioned throughout all stages of the research, via gender-sensitive participatory planning and diagnostic tools.

1.2 Quality and appropriateness of the training and of the two-way transfer of knowledge between the researcher and the host

Transfer of previously acquired knowledge to the participating organisations.

Oxford/UNAM. Throughout my academic career, I have received training in science communication theory and evaluation. I also have ample experience in organising events in many contexts (from astronomy camps to physics schools to international conferences) often with a focus on transferring STEM knowledge to young, underprivileged people. Oxford Physics excels in engaging thousands of people in science, locally (c.f. Marie Curious; Stargazing live) and internationally, (c.f. Global Jet Watch for Social Change; Zooniverse), however, little efforts are made to evaluate, and share the successes and failures of such ambitious activities with other disciplines. This is a common problem in science communication, and is especially crucial in light of the current STEM crisis. Thus, based on my expertise on outreach evaluation – I will transfer my knowledge to Oxford Physics via a dedicated workshop, which will enable physicists to carry out their own outreach with evaluation in mind. I will also organise an evaluation workshop at UNAM Physics, which similarly runs outreach activities in Namibia without evaluation practices in place, such as the mobile planetarium project.

¹⁹ D. Scott, et al. (2019) *Global tourism vulnerability to climate change*, *Annals of Tourism Research*, 77:49-61

²⁰ B. Bramwell, et al. (2017) *Twenty-five years of sustainable tourism and the Journal of Sustainable Tourism: looking back and moving forward*, *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 25(1):1-9

²¹ World Tourism Organization (2019), *Global Report on Women in Tourism – Second Edition*, UNWTO, Madrid

²² D. M. Alarcón & S. Cole (2019) *No sustainability for tourism without gender equality*, *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 27(7):903-919

²³ E. L. F. Schipper, et al. (2017). *Closing the knowledge gaps on gender and climate change for CCD*. In *Making Climate Compatible Development Happen* (pp. 44-65). Taylor and Francis Inc.

WRB and Visit Wester Ross are looking for tourism activities which put less pressure on the region during the summer peak times, and generate a more sustainable income for the local communities into the winter months. Thus, WRB is very keen to learn about DST and receive guidance on applying to the IDA for certified IDSP status, knowledge which I will transfer via focus-group meetings with the board and other local stakeholders. I will also offer astronomy training to local tour guides, which my current role in Namibia entails. Finally, I will dedicate time to creating awareness on the topic of light pollution via the existing networks that WRB has in the local area.

Knowledge transfer between the participating organisations and myself.

WRB. A community-led and owned NGO, WRB utilises research, education, and training to promote sustainable development between people and nature. As such, WRB is an ideal secondment for DARKSKY, supervised by the lead coordinator xxx on a daily basis for the first three months of the fellowship (WP 1.1). Via shadowing and weekly focus meetings, xxx will provide training in quantitative and qualitative research methods and community engagement issues, as well as extra support as interviews of the volunteers and employees in Scottish IDSPs begins (WP 2.1). For the rest of the fellowship I will be in regular monthly contact with WRB to assess the ongoing and remaining research, and support the analysis process.

UNAM Physics is a key partner of several astrophysics collaborations, and is currently developing DST via training tour guides and utilising networks with DSAs, tour guide associations and tourism ministers. The department is also in close contact with xxx, a tourism scholar at the International University of Management, who will provide further support and training in mixed methods as I implement the skills I learned at WRB and continue collecting WP 2.1 data. Thus, as one of the best countries in the world for DST, UNAM is favourably placed to facilitate tourism connections in Namibia and South Africa. During my time there, I will attend UNAM Physics' weekly meetings to highlight progress and transfer newfound knowledge. Upon my return to Oxford from UNAM, I will share my first-hand experience of carrying out social science research on astronomy for development in the Global South via a workshop and seminar. This is novel for Oxford Physics – where the focus has been on the implementation (and not research) of development projects.

Oxford Physics has a long and successful history of strong engagement in astronomy for development projects in Southern Africa. Thus, while at Oxford I will be predominantly based in Physics with xxx, with close ties to the School of Geography and the Environment, where co-supervisor xxx is based. The former will provide training in grant writing, project management and interview skills, and the latter will train me in gender issues, mixed methods research, and policy engagement – this will occur remotely via monthly meetings for the first year and via in-person meetings for the second year, twice a month. Moreover, Oxford is ranked second and seventh in the world for Social Sciences and Physics²⁴, and offers free access to the University's 100+ physical libraries, as well as all seminars and lectures. I will attend Social Sciences Division seminars and their monthly "A Pint of Ethics" meetups, and Oxford's dedicated online training on integrity and ethics will support me through the ethical review process. People and Organisational Development offers one-to-one career guidance, coaching and mentoring which will help me to achieve my career goals. In return, DARKSKY complements the cross-disciplinary nature of many Oxford activities, such as the Africa Oxford Initiative (AfOx). Furthermore, my time in Namibia will further reinforce the bond between UNAM and Oxford, and create additional avenues of knowledge exchange for AfOx, Oxford Physics, and the University as a whole. Thus, the University of Oxford has much to offer and to receive as the host of DARKSKY.

Overall, this fellowship will provide a wealth of opportunity for my personal and career development, while attaining core research skills in quantitative and qualitative methods, along with new transferable skills (e.g. community and policy engagement). In addition, the knowledge exchanged throughout the two years will directly lead to new, expansive ideas for capacity building projects which can be fed back into future funding applications. With these new experiences, I hope to inspire other new and exciting projects bringing social scientists and astrophysicists together, not only at the participating organisations but also worldwide.

1.3 Quality of the supervision and of the integration in the team/institution

Supervision. The supervisory team includes a diverse group of experts, at differing career stages and backgrounds, ensuring that the team's varied experience will be greatly complimentary. Moreover, the team are all personally committed to supervising my research project and career development.

²⁴ The Times Higher Education World University Rankings 2020, www.timeshighereducation.com/world-university-rankings/university-oxford [accessed 12/8/20]

xxx is at a very advanced stage of his career. He has two notable appointments within Oxford Physics. He is the PI of seven high-impact projects, attaining more than £1.6M of funding since 2013 (from the Science and Technology Facilities Council, Economic and Social Research Council, and Marie Curie FP7 ITN). xxx has been Co-I on another six projects, worth a combined value of more than £13M. He has given six plenary and review talks in the past six years and has more than refereed 60 publications, with a total of ~4,000 citations (H-index = 27). He is a collaboration member of several international organisations, including the Square Kilometre Array, the Cherenkov Telescope Array, and H.E.S.S. xxx is also responsible for the successful delivery of several Oxford-Africa projects (the Newton Fund Oxford-South Africa Ph.D. Exchange Programme, the DARA project, and the GCRF-funded project mentioned in Section 1.2). He has supervised eight PhD students and seven postdocs – the majority have gone onto fruitful and permanent careers in academia – and he is currently supervising one PhD student and four postdocs.

xxx is at mid-career stage. She is a researcher at Oxford's Environmental Change Institute, and Research Associate with the Overseas Development Institute (London) and the Stockholm Environment Institute Asia Centre. She has 87 publications with ~7800 citations (H-index = 34) and is Co-ordinating Lead Author of Chapter 18 of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change's Working Group II contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report. She is also co-Editor-in-Chief of the journal *Climate and Development* and on the editorial board of *World Development Perspectives* and *Global Transitions: Health Transitions*. She has successfully co-supervised two PhD students, and is currently co-supervising a third.

xxx is at a mid-advanced career stage. He was recently appointed as UNAM's Head of the Virtual Institute for Scientific Computing & Artificial Intelligence, and is the Head of the H.E.S.S. Research Unit. He is involved in numerous collaborations and was the Chair of the local and scientific organising committees of the 7th Annual Conference on High Energy Astrophysics in Southern Africa. Since 2014, xxx has been awarded €2M+ funding as PI and Co-I, and he received the UNAM Meritorious Award 2017 for Best Academic Performance. xxx has also been involved in numerous TV interviews (e.g. CNN and NBC), he has more than 140 refereed publications, with ~7,850 citations (H-index = 45), and he has co-supervised two PhD students, and is currently co-supervising four postdocs.

xxx is the lead coordinator of WRB, and has supervised eight people (including two PhD students and two postdocs). She was Co-I of the SHAPE (Sustainable Heritage Areas: Partnerships for Ecotourism) project (2017-2020), and she's a board member of the North West Highlands UNESCO Geopark. xxx also organised the Sustaining Wester Ross conference in March 2020.

Hosting arrangements and integration. During the fellowship, I will move three times within two years, and thus the hosting arrangements and integration are essential for the successful implementation of the project as well as my personal development. My previous experience in adapting to new institutions will be especially helpful; I am already well versed in adapting to new countries and institutes in short spaces of time (i.e. moving four times within the two-year Astromundus Masters programme). Regular meetings will be held online twice a month by all supervisors to discuss ideas, overcome obstacles, and ensure continuous support throughout. At the beginning of the project the supervisors and I will define a career development plan, which will include the attendance of workshops aimed at providing training in mixed methods, gender issues and transferable skills, in addition to planning for publications and participation in conferences.

WRB. Wester Ross is well equipped for the integration of its visitors, having hosted eight researchers in the past four years. Since the WRB is a small team, I will be immediately integrated with daily interaction with xxx. WRB also has extensive partnerships within Scotland and Europe, and regularly cooperates with policymakers, scientists, resource managers, private organisations and local communities whom I will be introduced to. Collaborating organisations include the School of Adventure Studies (West Highland College UHI); North West Highlands Geopark; Visit Wester Ross; Highlands and Islands Enterprise; and several members of the local council. Thus, the WRB is in a great position to not only provide training-through-research, but facilitate networking between numerous bodies and publics. WRB also brings international networking opportunities, via connections made during the SHAPE project, which spanned six countries, and the UNESCO's Man and the Biosphere (MAB) programme.

UNAM. The Physics Department at UNAM is experienced in hosting international academics, shown by the four international postdocs hired for the GCRF development project. I will be quickly integrated via weekly meetings attended by the whole department, ensuring that all parties gain maximum knowledge throughout. I will collaborate with the tourism industry and ministers in Namibia, via pre-existing networks,

including the Ministry of Environment, Forestry and Tourism; Namibia Scientific Society; and numerous tourism associations. International networking opportunities will be supported via close ties with the IAU Office of Astronomy for Development, which is greatly interested in DST and sustainability.

Oxford. There are several measures in place to ensure successful integration in the department and the University as a whole. Oxford's Newcomer's Club is dedicated to supporting new academics as they arrive and there are societies, such as the Oxford Research Staff Society which organises social and professional networking opportunities for researchers across the University. The Women in Physics Society also organises events for career development and provides a welcoming support network for new researchers at Oxford Physics. Furthermore, the department's Athena SWAN Silver Award (held since 2015) and Juno Champion status (held since 2016) demonstrates its commitment to providing an inclusive environment and improving equality and diversity. Finally, Oxford's Policy Engagement Network is a fantastic place to engage in policymaking locally, nationally and internationally which will further enhance research dissemination.

1.4 Potential of the researcher to reach or re-enforce professional maturity/independence during the fellowship

In my academic career thus far, I have demonstrated my independence via my academic achievements (two first-author papers and the 10+ invited international talks), undergraduate teaching, and supervising young people in astronomy. I have also designed and delivered science communication workshops across Europe and organised many different astrophysics events across the globe (from the UK to Finland to Palestine) and online. I am actively engaged in science policy events and workshops (e.g. Voice of the Future, Sense about Science) and personal development (i.e. the Transpeer Erasmus+ transnational project). This showcases my independence and eagerness to go outside of my comfort zone, learn new things and engage with multiple spheres outside of academia. During the fellowship, I will use my ambitious drive to push my boundaries in public and policy engagement, and to continue enriching my skills and development.

Likewise, my existing experience in astrophysics exemplifies my ability to become an independent academic. One year into my PhD I switched topics, gaining experience in analysing very different types of data. These existing analytical skills are very applicable to this study; even if the research is dissimilar to astrophysics, the underlying mathematics and statistics are similar. During my PhD I also spent considerable time studying the science of science communication, and working with social science PhD students. With their help, I produced a questionnaire for 300+ previous participants of the International Astronomical Youth Camp and carried out the analysis. The results were presented at numerous international conferences and published in *Nature Astronomy*. The new competencies and skills acquired during the fellowship will strengthen my foundation in applied research and pave the path towards my future career as an interdisciplinary researcher.

2.1 Enhancing the future career prospects of the researcher after the fellowship

My goal is to become an academic who contributes to a greener future via examining the intersection between astronomy and society. Since I started working on DST, I found that research is performed in isolation – there are no dedicated networks, conferences or events which connect the related disciplines together. Thus, this fellowship will help me to foster a new dark sky tourism network, so that I can harness the great potential for cooperation and collaboration in astronomy and society, by improving the transfer of knowledge. I am also excited by the opportunity to do some mentoring and teaching at Oxford and UNAM, and giving guest lectures, which will help me to gain experience needed for an independent career. Ultimately, I would like to forge my own cross-disciplinary research group, which this fellowship will undoubtedly help me to achieve.

In return, Oxford's dedicated coaching and mentoring services (offered by the People and Organisational Development unit and the MPLS division) will train me to achieve my ambitious goals. DARKSKY will provide concrete research experience in applied methods and transdisciplinary skills, improving my employability and career prospects both in and outside academia. The proposal will also contribute to the SDGs and the European Green Deal, as the EU strives to be the first climate-neutral continent. Moreover, I will benefit from expanding my network internationally, across academia, industry and policy which will be useful long into the future. The novel results will impact many other countries and communities carrying out astronomy for development projects. This is important to me and my future career beyond the fellowship, where I hope to make an impact across multiple sectors, disciplines, and continents.

2.2 Quality of the proposed measures to exploit and disseminate the project results

Scientific community. Due to the interdisciplinarity of DST and sustainability, the research project will yield exciting new insights across several fields. Novel results will be disseminated in high-impact journals and conferences across four main fields: tourism, sustainable development, science communication, and light pollution. All publications and presentations will acknowledge support received from MSCA, and will be in compliance with the open access rules. I plan to publish at least two **peer-reviewed papers** by the end of the fellowship in high-impact journals such as the *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* and *Nature Climate Change*. I will also disseminate the research at a minimum of three prestigious **international conferences**, such as Tourism Education Futures Initiative; EuroMAB; International Dark-Sky Association Annual Meeting; European Symposium for the Protection of the Night Sky; etc. **Industry and policy makers.** Using pre-established connections, the work will be communicated to relevant stakeholders in industry and policy internationally to disseminate the newfound knowledge. I will also utilise the WRB's close contacts with industry and decisionmakers in order to have an equally significant impact on local scales. The Oxford Policy Engagement Network also provides support for engaging with stakeholders. **Intellectual property rights** are not relevant, and thus, IP management will not be needed.

2.3. Quality of the proposed measures to communicate the project activities to different target audiences

Building on previous experience in outreach, science communication and journalism, I will engage with the public in a variety of ways throughout. As well as communicating my research, I will share my experience of carrying it out, how the scientific process works, and my journey to becoming a scientist as a woman and as the first and only person in my family to go to university. These aspects are important for humanising the scientists behind the science, and making scientists more relatable and trustworthy²⁵.

Writing. I will update my blog (astrophysicsgirl.com, more than 200 subscribers) 3-4 times a year. The blogs will contain research updates, as well as the experience of being a MSCA Fellow and transitioning from astrophysics to social science. I will use long-standing connections with other organisations (i.e. Royal Astronomical Society, International Dark-Sky Association, Africa Oxford Initiative) to write additional blogs and articles. Showcasing dark sky tourism and its direct impact on people and the world is crucial – these facts are often especially overlooked by the astronomy community. Finally, I will work hard to reach out to local and global press, making use of several connections already made by xxx at UNAM.

Social Media. I am an active communicator on Twitter (@astro_hsd, ~1,200 followers), and will use the platform to disseminate my research activities and experiences. I will develop my (astro)photography skills to share captivating photos of my work, to inspire and expand my audience. I am also interested in using Instagram as a tool for science communication. For all social media I will use well known hashtags related to the research project – such as #mariecuriefellows, #scicomm, #darkskies, and #lightpollution – alongside the @MSCAactions handle. I will also coordinate with related organisations and networks to help share and amplify the most interesting project updates.

Speaking. I will utilise my previous experience in public speaking and event organisation to communicate my activities with diverse audiences throughout the fellowship. I will organise public talks at WRB, UNAM and Oxford, making use of extensive previous connections. Oxford Physics, for example, already has a popular podcast, as well as an outreach group which reaches thousands of people annually. I will also coordinate with local radio/university stations and newspapers to reach new audiences, and take part in annual outreach events like Stargazing Live and Marie Curious. Finally, I will host an online webinar, to reach the public worldwide, and give a platform for other DST Early Career Researchers to showcase their work.

Photojournalism. Science communication through photojournalism is an innovative form of sharing research, and has the scope for reaching entirely new audiences²⁶. I will publish photojournalist pieces in nature-based magazines which have large international readerships (e.g. Another Escape, Bumble, Ernest, Run Wild). This has the potential to be very thought-provoking, and could also open up opportunities to work directly with other artists and photographers. My experience as a science journalist intern at the European Southern Observatory and Editor-in-Chief of a student physics journal will help me to implement this.

²⁵ L. Neeley, et al. (2020) *Linking Scholarship and Practice: Narrative and Identity in Science*. Front. Commun. 5:35.

²⁶ J. Palakovich Carr, (2012) *Science Photography: Communicating Research through Photos*, BioScience, 62(5): 458–459

3.1 Coherence and effectiveness of the work plan, including appropriateness of the allocation of tasks and resources

The major aspects of the research involve quantitative and qualitative studies, and the design of a carbon footprint model. Together with the supervisory team, I will define a career development plan at the start of the fellowship to determine the training needed for the research. This will include several workshops in scientific and transferable skills, including mixed methods, statistics, gender aspects, and leadership and management training. In addition, I will formulate a data management plan. The work plan addresses four main packages, as shown in the Gantt Chart below. The plan has been designed in order to maximise efficiency, whereby milestones are appropriately placed to address any unexpected issues. Moreover, well in advance of the beginning of the project I will submit my ethics application, in order to minimise any possible delays. The final research project (WP 2.4) is particularly ambitious, and may continue beyond the fellowship on my journey to independence if necessary.

While DARKSKY is demanding, the combined expertise of the host and myself makes it feasible and achievable. Furthermore, the host institution is a world-class centre of scientific research, with a wide range of core facilities to support the proposed work as well as Research Offices with extensive experience in project management of FP7 and H2020 grants. These combined facilities make this research environment ideal for the success of this ambitious proposal.

WP	TASK TITLE	YEAR ONE												YEAR TWO											
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	Location																								
1.1	Secondment (Wester Ross Biosphere)			D1.1																					
1.2	Outgoing phase (University of Namibia)												D1.2												
1.3	Incoming phase (University of Oxford)																								D1.3
2	Research Projects																								
2.1	Qualitative study (interviews)													M2.1											D2.1
2.2	Longitudinal surveys														M2.2										D2.2
2.3	Grey literature study												M2.3												D2.3
2.4	Carbon footprint model design																								M2.4
																									D2.4
3	Research Dissemination and Communication																								
3.1	Academia (conferences and publications)													M3.1a											D3.1a
																									M3.1b
3.2	Industry and decisionmakers			D3.2a																					D3.2b
																									D3.2c
3.3	Outreach and public engagement			D3.3a																					D3.3c
																									D3.3c
4	Training and Management																								
4.1	Training courses and programmes			D4.1a																					M4.1
																									D4.1b
4.2	Project and risk management																								M4.2a
																									M4.2b
																									M4.2c
																									D4.2

3.2 Appropriateness of the management structure and procedures, including risk management

Organisation, management structure, and progress monitoring mechanisms. During the fellowship, I will have access to all the necessary structures to support the proposed work. While having complete autonomy, I will take the lead in managing the project and its scientific aspects, and frequently meet online with the supervisory team (at least monthly) to monitor progress, discuss ideas and decide on the best courses of action when challenges arise. Oxford Physics and xxx will also facilitate the management of my interactions with Oxford and vice-versa while I am elsewhere, which will occur via the regular meetings. Institute seminars at Oxford Physics and the School of Geography and the Environment will provide further opportunities to discuss the project with other experienced researchers in the field, and extend my dark sky tourism network.

Oxford Physics Grants and the Research Services EC team will aid the financial management of the project, and Research Services/HR will help with the necessary agreements with the partner organisations (namely UNAM and WRB). Both teams are highly experienced, having managed more than 30 Marie Curie Actions under FP7 in Physics alone, as well as 600+ H2020 grants across the University. The Research Facilitation Office will assist me with managing the project financially, to ensure the correct implementation of the project and to allow me to concentrate on the project. Finally, WRB/UNAM will support my mobility in moving to Scotland/Namibia and help me to arrange accommodation, and work permits and visas where required.

Research/admin risks. The preparation and signature of grant agreements for the fellowship will be carried out by the Research Services EC and Oxford Physics HR team. To date, Oxford is a participant of 631 Horizon 2020 projects, 197 MSCA IFs as host, and 45 successful Horizon 2020 ITNs. At any given time, the University is supporting ~100 MSCA research fellows. The proposed work plan is ambitious but achievable – it combines my strengths, skills and knowledge with the expertise of the participating organisations. Potential risks have been identified and contingency plans proposed in the unlikely event that these risks materialise:

- The research relies on a successful ethics application. Before the project begins, I will be guided by the Research Services Ethics team, and will make use of Oxford's online research integrity course and/or face-to-face ethics training courses. This will ensure that the application can be filed several months before the project begins to minimise any possible delays. In addition to Oxford's dedicated staff, I will work with xxx (co-supervisor) and xxx at WRB to ensure that the application fulfils all the necessary requirements. The research is anticipated to be low-risk and straightforward and thus the ethical review process is relatively quick (up to 30 days).
- The fellowship involves spending nine months in Namibia, based at UNAM, for which a visa and work permit will be required. To minimise delays the process will be started as soon as the outcome of the fellowship is known. With the help of UNAM, xxx and xxx, I am currently applying for a Namibian work permit and visa right now, and so I will know exactly the steps needed in order to be successful, which will reduce the risks of my application being delayed.
- The future situation regarding covid-19 is still very much unknown. It may be that international travel, face-to-face meetings, and gatherings of large groups in 2022-2023 are still not possible or have severe limitations. This may pose risks for travelling to Namibia, and for conducting interviews face-to-face – if needed, interviews can easily be conducted online. There may be additional challenges with attending conferences/seminars, interacting with colleagues and growing my network if covid-19 continues to pose a threat. In this scenario, I will find online alternatives to achieve these activities, as I have been doing in recent months.

3.3 Appropriateness of the institutional environment (infrastructure)

The University of Oxford is a world-class centre of scientific research, with a wide range of core facilities to support the proposed work. The following facilities will greatly benefit the proposed project:

- Assistance with completing the Marie Curie grant agreement and all reporting requirements via a dedicated Oxford European and International Team.
- Assistance with coordinating with UNAM and WRB to implement the outgoing phases of the fellowship.
- Assistance with moving to Oxford via the Oxford University Welcome Service.

- Dedicated assistance and training from Research Services Ethics team to obtain ethical clearance.
- Free access to specialist libraries and collections within Oxford.
- Free courses offered through the Oxford Learning Institute, which trains academics in research and transferable skills such as leadership and project management.
- Free mentoring and coaching offered by POD (People and Organisational Development) which provides alternative and effective development opportunities for researchers to overcome obstacles, gain insights and achieve goals.
- Training and development offered by MPLS (the Mathematics, Physics, and Life Sciences division), such as the RisingWISE enterprise course and the Oxford Women's Development Programme.
- Specific networks which support and mentor women, such as MPLS Women's Network, OxWEST (Oxford Women in Engineering, Science, and Technology), and the Oxford Women in Physics Society.
- Regular career development reviews and focused one-to-one career support for ECRs offered by the Oxford University Careers Service, including additional support from Research Facilitators to help with future applications.
- Opportunities to take part in annual outreach events, like Marie Curious (a one-day science event for 11-14 year-old girls with exciting hands-on workshops and activities) and its yearly Stargazing live event which attracts 1,200+ members of the public.
- Interactions with a wide range of experts based at Oxford Physics, the wider University, and high-profile academics who visit the University.
- The Beecroft building: a state-of-the-art, £50M physics building opened in 2018 which was designed specially to foster collaborative working. Engaging cross-disciplinary meetings will be held here.
- Infrastructure in the Astrophysics department which provides office space and places for interactive meetings.

The Universities of Namibia and Oxford will also be able to offer:

- Provision of desk space, including unrestricted access to supported PC facilities, and an email account and telephone number.
- Assistance with HR issues, payroll and pension. UNAM also has a team dedicated to helping the work permit and visa application process.

The Wester Ross Biosphere will support:

- The logistics of the secondment phase of the project, by arranging accommodation and desk space at the Anancaun Field Station in the Beinn Eighe National Nature Reserve, in close proximity to WRB.
- The facilitation of interactions with the local communities, tourism companies, policymakers in Wester Ross and their existing networks further afield.

In summary, the proposed work is expected to generate high quality, novel results of wide interest. While the project is ambitious, the combination of my proven ability together with the excellent research environment and expert supervision will allow them to be achieved. Furthermore, the proposal provides the additional training, knowledge and research experience required for me to achieve my career goal of establishing my own interdisciplinary research group.

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